

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL PROBLEMS OF TEACHING LAW IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article gives an idea of the law and the methodology of teaching law. Scientific and theoretical problems of teaching law in the education system are also highlighted.

Keywords: education, law, civil society, legal education, legal culture.

НАУЧНО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ПРАВА В СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация: В статье дается представление о праве и методике преподавания права. Также освещаются научно-теоретические проблемы преподавания права в системе образования.

Ключевые слова: образование, право, гражданское общество, правовое образование, правовая культура.

INTRODUCTION

With the main directions of modernizing the education sector in our country, increasing the number of places allocated to higher education year by year, and ensuring wider involvement of young people in the education system, as noted in Decree No. determines the relevance of the science of law in education.

Uzbekistan has entered a new stage of development based on the principle of "From national revival to national rise". The intensity of the new era is making clear and strict demands on the education system.

Within the framework of these requirements, the material and moral conditions of pedagogues in the field of education are radically improved, and modern technologies for improving the quality of education are being introduced.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Education and training cannot be separated from each other, these two processes are harmonious, organized on a continuous basis only when they are polite, have moral qualities, high spirituality, and at the same time are knowledgeable, intelligent, mentally and physically healthy, have a broad outlook and thinking, modern profession. cultivates patriotic young people who are masters of the craft [1.]. If we pay attention to the name of 2020, that is, the year of development of science, enlightenment and digital economy, we can see that the development of state programs and the education of our children are focused on the relevant clauses. Education of a mature generation is mentioned in the relevant clauses of the state programs. It is known that any independent state can achieve high development only if it has a strong moral foundation. For this purpose, we are introducing the subject of "Education" for the first time in general education schools as part of the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education"[2.]. It should be noted that the issue of supporting talented and talented youth is always in the center of attention.

The Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the measures to gradually implement the science of "Education" in general secondary educational institutions" was adopted.

It was determined that in general secondary educational institutions, the single subject "Education" combining the subjects "Etiquette", "Feeling of the Motherland", "The idea of

national independence and the foundations of spirituality" and "History of world religions" in the 1st - 9th grades - from the 2020/2021 academic year. , and in the 10th - 11th grades - from the 2021/2022 academic year, it should be gradually implemented within the general hours allocated to subjects.

With this, taking into account the age and psychophysiological characteristics of the students of general secondary educational institutions, it was aimed to instill universal human values and high spirituality in their minds, to educate them in the spirit of patriotism and humanitarianism, to organize spiritual and educational work in general secondary educational institutions on a new basis.

The complex part of the processes related to raising the morale of our society is that we have to solve many problems in the path of social and political development, both theoretically and practically, relying only on our own strength and potential.

The purpose of teaching the subject is to acquaint students with the complex of necessary information of law. At the same time, it helps students to think logically, draw correct conclusions, and improve their legal culture.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The tasks of teaching science are to enrich the imagination of young people about the structure and components of the science of law, the history of its development and its role in the development of society, the role of the science of law in humanitarian sciences.

Law students:

- That human rights are the highest value;
- About the concept of child rights;
- To have an idea about legal literacy;
- Protection of civil society in the process of legal culture development;
- increasing scientific and legal literacy within the framework of the "family-neighborhood-educational institution" model in a certain process;
- objects should have the skills to use mathematical symbols to express quantitative and qualitative relationships.

At the new stage of the development of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main task of educational institutions is to prepare specialists who can adapt to the changing production conditions at the level of world requirements, not to recognize the amount of information provided as the main factor in this process, but to form a creative approach to them and educate qualities such as independent thinking.

DISCUSSION

New high tasks were set before the educational system. To fulfill such high tasks, the methodology is required to be enriched with pedagogical technologies. Today, high efficiency is demanded from every pedagogue. However, the rapid development of science, increasing the amount of knowledge, requires a new approach from the teacher. Today, a pedagogue should be able to achieve high efficiency using old methods. That is why we need to introduce students to new pedagogical technologies and equip them with skills in this regard. Future teachers need to be familiar not only with the methodology, but also with pedagogical technologies and reach the level of being able to use them easily.

Pedagogical technologies are created in a fundamentally different way from traditional education. It requires a mutually closed loop and consistent interdependence. Defined goals

provide great opportunities for the educator to define control work, evaluate and determine methods. All stages are subject to one goal and guarantee a high result.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, further improvement of pedagogical technologies, development of new technologies is required. Pedagogical technologies, especially in terms of education, are poorly developed. Certain technologies lack precision. Today, the demands on the skills of the teacher are increasing. The teacher is required not only to manage his own psyche and speech culture, but also to manage the mental state of his students. In order to fulfill this task, the pedagogue should study the subtle aspects of the student's psyche and find a way to the heart of each student. For this, every pedagogue should work tirelessly on himself.

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